

UPGRADED MULTIPROBE SAMPLE INSERTS FOR THIN FILM SRF CAVITY DEVELOPMENTS*

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Abstract

Optimisation of thin film (TF) coating parameters for producing SRF cavities requires rapid testing of superconducting properties. A dedicated multiprobe facility built at Daresbury Lab, based on a liquid He free cryocooler, allows such measurements to be performed. The facility has vacuum tubular inserts where the sample probe is loaded and cooled with He gas. The experimental inserts were either newly built or upgraded: (1) A DC resistance experiment allows measurements of critical temperature (T_c) and residual resistance ratio (RRR) on non-conductive substrates (e.g. sapphire). A newly designed insert allows better temperature control and easier sample change. (2) A new insert for magnetic field measurements of T_c on both conductive and non-conductive substrates. (3) An existing insert for planar magnetic field penetration experiments was significantly redesigned. It operates at lower temperatures (> 5.5 K), parallel magnetic fields < 600 mT, increased sensitivity, and enables measurements of field of first flux penetration (B_{fp}) and T_c on various substrates: copper and sapphire, the latter of which was impossible to measure with an older design.

INTRODUCTION

Thin film (TF) coated superconducting radio frequency (SRF) cavities are under development in a number of accelerator laboratories worldwide [1, 2]. Before a TF coating can be produced on an RF cavity, the deposition process is optimised on small samples. These samples are then evaluated with surface analysis and cryogenic techniques.

At Daresbury Laboratory (DL), three in-house developed facilities based on two stage 4 K LHe-free cryocoolers have been built. These are used to evaluate the superconducting (SC) properties of TFs deposited on both conductive and non-conductive substrates [3]. Two of these facilities measure samples under: DC conditions [4, 5] or RF conditions [6–8].

The third facility is a multiprobe cryostat for quick tests [9]. Inside this facility, two tubes, known as Vacuum Tubular Inserts (VTI), are thermally connected to the main cryogenic stages. The VTIs are filled with He gas during sample loading and removal, without the need to warm and vent the main chamber. This process enables multiple sample loads

and tests per day. This paper describes recent upgrades on three sample inserts used in the multiprobe facility.

SAMPLE INSERTS

Four-Point Probe

The purpose of a Four-Point Probe (FPP) is a quick, first evaluation of the deposited TF sample (on non-conducting substrate) to answer: whether the sample is SC, what is its critical temperature (T_c) and residual resistance ratio (RRR). The sample holder of the FPP insert was redesigned (Fig. 1) to allow a wider range of sample sizes, easier sample change, more accurate temperature readings and easier rewiring.

Figure 1: FPP sample holder. (a) Sample mount, (b) PCB.

The sample holder a Cu rod (20 mm dia., 60 mm length). This ensures that the whole piece is thermalised. A heater (10- Ω resistor) and a Cernox thermometer (Lake Shore CX-1050-CU-HT-1.4L) are located at the bottom and mounted on opposite sides. The 4-point contact piece is a square spring-loaded PCB with 2.54 mm contact pitch. Two pins apply a current (I_{app}) and two measure the voltage. It is mounted on a PCB along with other wiring and cables to the top of the insert. A sample (max 7 mm \times 7 mm) is mounted opposite the PCB, so its TF coated side is in contact with the 4 pins. It is held in place with a Cu plate which also ensures strong thermalisation with the Cu rod. It operates at sample temperatures in the range of $4\text{ K} \leq T_s \leq 80\text{ K}$.

An example of T_c measurements of V_3Si , NbN and NbTiN (at $I_{app} = 1$ mA) are shown in Fig. 2. T_c is measured at 50% maximum (with the 10% and 90% points defining the transition width). Here, 14.24 ± 0.10 K for V_3Si , $T_c = 15.74 \pm 0.25$ K for NbN and $T_c = 16.48 \pm 0.02$ K for NbTiN. The optimal temperature ramp rate was found by

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comparing the results of different rates of ramp up/down cycles for the same sample. It was found that a $dT_s/dt = 0.1$ K/min ensures consistent measurements for a ramp up/down cycle (with an accuracy ± 0.01 K). The agreement between measurements of increasing and decreasing temperature sweeps also indicate that T_s and the thermometer temperature are the same.

Figure 2: T_c measurements with the FPP for NbN and V_3Si .

It should be noted that this system can measure T_c and RRR on a TF sample ($< 5 \mu m$) only. Thicker samples would require a higher I_{app} , another contact design, and/or a larger distance between the pins. The method is suitable only for TFs on electrically non-conductive substrates (e.g. sapphire). In general, the typical measurement time at 3 different currents (to extrapolate to $I_{app} = 0$) is 2 – 3 hours.

Magnetic T_c

The T_c of the samples deposited on electrically conductive substrates (i.e. Cu and Nb) can be measured with magnetic methods. The main idea for a new insert (Fig. 3) is to place a sample (max $10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$) at the end of a coil and apply a DC magnetic field (B_{app}). Measurements of magnetic field are made using two Hall probes (Lakeshore HGCA-3020): in the bore of the coil (B_1) and on the other side of the sample (B_2). The coil is wound with 0.1 mm wire with a total number of turns $N = 256$, allowing $B \approx 4.5 \text{ mT}$ ($I_{app} = 100 \text{ mA}$).

Figure 3: The magnetic T_c sample holder.

An example of B_2/B_1 measurements of Nb_3Sn are shown in Fig. 4 for $B_{app} = 12 \text{ mT}$. T_c is calculated from the 50%

maximum point (with 10% and 90% points for the transition width). Here, $T_c = 15.49^{+0.66}_{-0.52} \text{ K}$. Typically, multiple sweeps of T_s are recorded at different values of B_{app} and linearly fitted as a function T_s^2 . Extrapolation to $B_{app} = 0$ allows calculation of T_c using the same method as with the magnetic field penetration insert. The typical time required for sample measurements at 3 different currents in the coil, i.e. with 3 different magnetic fields (to extrapolate to $B_{app} = 0$) is 2 – 3 hours.

Figure 4: B_2/B_1 vs T_s measured with the magnetic T_c insert for Nb_3Sn .

Magnetic Field Penetration

Magnetic Field Penetration (MFP) measurements are based on the simple idea of simultaneously applying a magnetic field: (a) parallel to the sample surface, (b) from one side of the sample (i.e. similar to the magnetic field in an RF cavity) and (c) locally (within an area $<$ sample size) to avoid or minimise the leakage of magnetic field around the sample. Two facilities have been designed and built at DL for MFP measurements: (a) an MFP insert for the multiprobe facility [10, 11] and (b) a dedicated MFP facility [4, 5].

Figure 5: The upgraded MFP sample holder (heaters - H_1-H_4 , thermometers - T_1 and T_2).

The layout of the MFP insert sample holder is shown in Fig. 5. The magnetic field is generated with a C-shaped magnet with 10 mm × 10 mm poles and a 2 mm gap between them. The applied magnetic field (B_1) is measured in the gap between the poles with a Hall probe (HP1), and the penetrated field (B_2) is detected on the other side of the sample (max 50 mm dia., 0.5 – 2 mm thick) with another Hall probe (HP2). The Hall probes are Lakeshore HGCT-3020. Recently, the MFP insert was redesigned and tested with two main modifications: (a) Increased length of the insert to reach a lower T_s , (b) magnetic shields (MS1 and MS2) around HP2. Smaller samples can also be evaluated, but not < 30 mm in any dimension.

Figure 6 shows an example of the raw data obtained with a 50 mm dia. bulk Nb disk. Measurements of field of first flux penetration (B_{fp}) are made at each value of T_s . This is defined as when $B_2 = 0.1$ mT. A linear fit to $B_{fp}(T_s^2)$ (Fig. 7) allows for an estimation of $B_{fp}(0\text{ K})$ and T_c . For this sample: $B_{fp}(0\text{ K}) = 514.6$ mT and $T_c = 9.23$ K using this method.

Figure 6: B_1 vs B_2 of a bulk Nb sample with the MFP insert.

Figure 7: B_{fp} vs T_s^2 for the bulk Nb sample with a linear fit to estimate $B_{fp}(0\text{ K})$ and T_c .

The main characteristics of this upgraded insert are: $T_s \geq 5.5$ K, applied magnetic field $0 \leq B_{app} \leq 600$ mT, magnetic field sensitivity $10\ \mu\text{T}$ and typical time required for full sample evaluation of B_{fp} and T_c is 1 day.

LABVIEW AUTOMATED DATA ACQUISITION

Automated data acquisition is essential to standardise the measurement procedure and free up the time of the staff for data analysis. For data recording, LabVIEW is used to allow for a full data set for the sample to be collected without human intervention. Therefore, measurements can be performed continuously at any time of the day, allowing the most efficient use of the multiprobe facility.

DISCUSSION

Enabling SC sample evaluation is essential for developing TF superconductors for SRF cavities. The three inserts described in this paper provide a complete set for initial evaluation on small planar samples.

The FPP and Magnetic T_c inserts are critically important to address: (a) Is the sample superconducting? (b) If yes, what is its T_c and RRR ? The properties of a TF deposited on different substrates (e.g. sapphire and Cu) could be different. The FPP is good for measuring a TF sample on sapphire, but to measure a TF on Cu, Kapton tape and nitric acid must be used to remove the TF beforehand. The question of how etching affects the TF properties remains open. A new Magnetic T_c insert avoids this work and makes the test faster and more reliable.

The MFP insert provides evaluation at higher B fields, but requires slightly larger samples than the other inserts. Compared to the dedicated MPF facility, the MPF insert is limited to a maximum sample size and cannot reach sample temperatures below 5.5 K (compared to 2.5 K in the MFP facility). However, the measurements can be performed in a shorter time: 1 day instead of 2 days.

CONCLUSIONS

Three experimental inserts were newly constructed or upgraded for operation with a multiprobe facility. (1) A DC resistance experiment allows measurements of T_c and RRR on non-conductive substrates, newly designed for better temperature control and easier sample change. (2) A new insert for magnetic field measurements of T_c on both conductive and non-conductive substrates. (3) An existing insert for magnetic field penetration experiments was significantly redesigned. Compared to previously, it operates at lower temperatures (> 5.5 K), parallel magnetic fields < 600 mT, increased sensitivity and enables measurements of B_{fp} and T_c on various substrates. Magnetic shielding of the Hall probe allows for an improved accuracy and simpler analysis of the results.

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